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Investigations on Cytocompatibility and In Vitro Corrosion Evaluation Stir-Cast Mg-1Sn-xHA Composites for Orthopaedic Applications

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Abstract

Objectives: The present investigation intends to explore the effect of hydroxyapatite content on the cytocompatibility and in vitro corrosion behaviour of stir-cast Mg-1Sn-xHA composites that might be used as orthopaedic implants.

Methods: Composites of Mg-1Sn-xHA (3, 6, 9 and 12 wt.%) have been created via stir casting; mass loss, corrosion rate, pH variance and surface morphology were also measured to evaluate in vitro corrosion in phosphate-buffered saline at 37°C for 24, 72 and 216 hours. The test was conducted using MG-63 cells and optical microscopy. The Mg-1Sn alloy was used as a control.

Findings: Research confirms that Mg is intrinsically susceptible to corrosion in physiological conditions, since the Mg-1Sn alloy degraded quickly, became significantly alkaline and had decreased cell viability. Hydroxyapatite slows corrosion and stabilises pH by allowing compact Ca-P-rich protective layers to develop more easily. Among all the compositions that were tested, Mg-1Sn-9HA had the best corrosion rate, with the lowest rate of mass loss and the most stable pH evolution. It also had the highest MG-63 cell survival (95%) and extensive cellular morphology. In comparison to materials with lower HA concentrations, our findings show that bioactive ceramic reinforcement in magnesium matrices is beneficial. At 12 wt.% HA, there was a slight decrease because the particles clumped together and damaged the interface. To improve biodegradable Mg-based composites, a systematic understanding of the interaction between HA content, degradation behaviour and biological response is essential.

Novelty: The present research reveals that stir-cast Mg-Sn composites with a recommended HA concentration of 9 wt.% are biodegradable orthopaedic implants that are both non-toxic and corrosion-resistant.

Keywords: Biodegradable magnesium; Mg-Sn-HA composites; Stir casting; In vitro corrosion; Cytocompatibility

1 Introduction

Biodegradable magnesium (Mg) alloys are considered advanced materials for lightweight orthopaedic implants, attributed to their low density, compatibility with the elastic modulus of the bone and advantageous biocompatibility^{(1), (2), (3)}. Comprehensive and advanced reviews provide insight into alloy design methodologies, corrosion mechanisms, and clinical challenges associated with Mg-based biomaterials⁽⁴⁾. However, the rapid deterioration in chloride-containing physiological conditions continues to be the primary constraint, resulting in early mechanical failure, the formation of hydrogen, and localized alkalization^{(4), (5)}.

Mg–Sn alloys have drawn considerable attention within alloying systems due to the formation of the Mg₂Sn intermetallic phase, which improves grain refinement, hardness, and corrosion resistance while avoiding the inclusion of cytotoxic elements^{(6), (7)}. Mg–1Sn compositions exhibit enhanced degradation stability in comparison to pure Mg⁽⁸⁾. Still, surface corrosion prevention and microstructure homogeneity are essential in order to achieve corrosion control and biological compatibility.

By incorporating hydroxyapatite (HA), a ceramic made of calcium phosphate that shares chemical similarities with bone minerals, into magnesium matrices, the bioactivity and corrosion stability of the materials are enhanced^{(9), (10)}. In-situ formation of Ca-P-rich apatite surfaces during immersion is made easier by HA reinforcement; this reduces degradation and improves cell adhesion⁽¹¹⁾. Squeeze casting, spark plasma sintering, ultrasonic-assisted casting, and plasma electrolytic oxidation are some of the fabrication processes that have been explored for Mg-HA and Mg-Sn-HA systems^{(12), (13), (14), (15), (16), (17)}. In addition, Zn-Mg-HA composites and other hybrid biodegradable systems have demonstrated improved biocompatibility and corrosion resistance by surface composite engineering via friction stir processing^{(18), (19)}.

Squeeze-cast Mg-Sn-HA composites exhibit potential, although optimization of the reinforcing percentage is not yet systematically addressed⁽²⁰⁾. In spite of all this progress, there are still three major things missing: (i) a way to optimize the amount of HA in Mg-1Sn matrices within a specific range of compositions; (ii) a way to quantify the relationship between the degradation mechanism, surface morphology modification, pH stability, cytocompatibility and (iii) a way to test these systems using fabrication methods that are suitable for producing large quantities of implants⁽¹⁸⁾.

The purpose of this research is to employ stir casting to create Mg-1Sn-xHA composites, where x ranges from 3 to 12%wt. It thoroughly assesses their biological compatibility with MG-63 and corrosion behaviour in vitro. The major objective of the work is to determine the optimal HA percentage for biodegradable orthopaedic implants by determining the link between the composition, structure, and characteristics. This fraction should successfully prevent corrosion while maintaining biological performance.

2 Methodology

2.1 Composite Fabrication

The structure of the matrix was developed by combining pure magnesium (99.9 wt.%) enhanced with tin as an alloying element and reinforced with hydroxyapatite (HA, Ca₁₀(PO₄)₆(OH)₂). For the fabrication of Mg-1Sn-xHA composites with 3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.% HA, the stir casting technique was used, which is known for its ease of use, scalability, and efficiency in making bulk metal matrix composites⁽²¹⁾.

A graphite crucible was used to melt magnesium ingots in an argon environment at temperatures between 720 and 750 °C, reducing the probability of oxidation⁽³⁾. Obtaining a uniform Mg-1Sn alloy required adding Sn while mechanically stirring the mixture. Incorporating Mg₂Sn into the solidification process enhances corrosion resistance and helps refine the microstructure^{(6), (7)}.

To improve its wettability and make it easier to remove moisture, HA powder was preheated to a temperature between 300 and 400 °C⁽⁸⁾. The preheated HA was incrementally added to the melt and was stirred at a speed of 400–600 rpm for a duration of 8–10 minutes to achieve uniform dispersion⁽¹²⁾. The molten metal was poured into preheated molds and permitted to solidify under natural circumstances^{(14), (17)}. [Table 1] provides a summary of the specific parameters used in the stir-casting process.

2.2 Sample Preparation

Cylindrical specimens with a diameter of 10 mm and a thickness of 3 mm were machined for the purpose of testing. Surfaces underwent a sequential grinding process using SiC papers with grits ranging from 600 to 2000. Following grinding, the surfaces were polished, subjected to ultrasonic cleaning in ethanol, rinsed with distilled water, dried, and subsequently stored in a desiccator^{(3), (9)}.

Table 1. Stir-casting parameters for Mg–1Sn–xHA composites

Process Parameter	Range	Justification
Magnesium purity	99.9 wt.%	Ensures minimal impurity-driven corrosion and consistent baseline properties
Tin content	1 wt.%	Promotes Mg ₂ Sn formation for grain refinement and mechanical strengthening
HA content (x)	3, 6, 9, 12 wt.%	To study the effect of reinforcement fraction on corrosion and cytocompatibility
Melting temperature	720–750°C	Ensures complete melting of Mg and dissolution of Sn
Atmosphere	Argon (inert)	Prevents oxidation and burning of molten Mg
HA preheating temperature	300–400°C	Removes moisture and improves wettability with Mg melt
Stirring speed	400–600 rpm	Achieves uniform dispersion of HA particles
Stirring duration	8–10 min	Minimizes particle agglomeration and porosity
Stirrer type	Graphite-coated stainless steel	Prevents iron contamination and melt reaction
Mold temperature	Preheated (200°C)	Reduces thermal shock and casting defects
Solidification condition	Ambient cooling	Enables formation of Mg ₂ Sn and uniform matrix structure

2.3 In Vitro Corrosion Testing

Static immersion tests were conducted in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS, pH ≈ 7.4) at a temperature of 37 ± 0.5 °C to replicate physiological conditions^{(3), (18)}. Samples have undergone immersion for durations of 24, 72, and 216 hours. [Figure 1] The sample before immersion and the experimental immersion setup are shown.

Fig 1. The sample before immersion and the setup of experimental immersion

Mass loss (ΔW) was calculated by measuring the weight differences between the initial and final immersion. The corrosion rate (CR) was determined using the following formula:

$$CR = \frac{K \times \Delta W}{A \times t \times \rho} \tag{1}$$

ΔW represents mass loss (g), A denotes exposed surface area (cm²), t indicates immersion time (h), ρ signifies density (g/cm³), and K is a constant valued at 10.12.

2.4 Cytocompatibility Assessment

The evaluation of cytocompatibility was conducted via MG-63 osteoblast-like cells through the MTT assay^{(8), (9)}. Extraction media were formulated in accordance with the specifications outlined in ISO 10993-5 recommendations⁽²²⁾. Cells underwent incubation with extracts from the sample for a duration of 24 hours. MTT reagent was introduced and incubated for a duration of 3 to 4 hours to facilitate the growth of crystals of formazan⁽²²⁾. Crystals were solubilized in DMSO, and absorption was quantified at a wavelength of 570 nm. Cell viability was quantified as a percentage in comparison to the control group^{(12), (13)}.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 In Vitro Corrosion Behaviour

3.1.1. Mass Loss and Corrosion Rate Analysis

The in vitro degradation behaviour of Mg–1Sn alloy and Mg–1Sn–xHA (where x = 3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.%) composites has been investigated via immersion testing in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at a temperature of 37 °C. The mass loss results presented in [Figure 2a] demonstrate that the unreinforced Mg–1Sn alloy shows the highest degradation rate across all immersion durations. The previous studies on Mg–Sn alloys, this behaviour shows that in chloride environments, insufficient surface passivation causes Mg dissolution to rise and porous Mg(OH)₂ to form.

The addition of HA results in a notable decrease in mass loss, particularly at moderate reinforcement levels. At 72 and 216 hours, Mg–1Sn–9HA shows the least mass loss compared to the other compositions, suggesting improved corrosion resistance. Improvements in Mg–Sn–HA combinations produced through squeeze casting have been observed. Nevertheless, the majority of research has concentrated on constant HA contents, lacking systematic optimization across various reinforcement levels. This study establishes a specific compositional variability range of 3–12 wt.% HA and identifies 9 wt.% as the most effective fraction for controlling degradation under constant immersion conditions.

The estimated values of the corrosion rate, as illustrated in [Figure 2b], validate the above finding. A temporary decrease in the corrosion rate observed at 72 hours is associated with the development of a semi-protective corrosion layer consisting of Mg(OH)₂ and Ca–P-rich phases. Similar Ca–P deposition mechanisms have been observed for Mg–HA composites produced through spark plasma sintering and modification of the surface methods. The current stir-cast method effectively achieves comparable corrosion mitigation through a bulk reinforcement methodology, as opposed to post-surface treatment, thereby illustrating processing scalability.

Fig 2. (a) shows the mass loss of the Mg-1Sn alloy and the Mg-1Sn-xHA composite subjected to different immersion times. (b) Illustration of the corrosion rates calculated from the mass loss data.

Corrosion rates increase at 216 hours resulting from localized film breakdown. Mg–1Sn–9HA exhibits least corrosion rate when compared to all other compositions. In comparison, Mg–1Sn–12HA exhibits a moderate rise in degradation rate, probably attributed to the agglomeration of HA and micro-galvanic coupling occurring at the interfaces between the reinforcement and

the matrix. This statement verifies that high levels of ceramic loading can risk interfacial continuation, a phenomenon similarly noted in magnesium-based hybrid systems.

3.1.2. pH variation of the immersion medium

The corrosion results are further confirmed by the fact that the immersion environment's pH may vary [Figure 3]. The most rapid magnesium dissolution and excessive hydroxyl ion generation is observed in the Mg-1Sn alloy, which is also characterized by the most significant rise in pH. HA-reinforced composites, particularly Mg-1Sn-9HA, demonstrate an enhanced alkalization process, with low pH rise seen after immersion on a periodic interval.

Fig 3. The immersion solution's pH level fluctuates periodically.

Hydroxyl ions and HA-mediated precipitation of calcium phosphate are the molecular mechanisms responsible for the buffering impact. Similar buffering processes shown in prior studies on HA-coated Mg and Mg-HA composites however, these systems were based on surface coatings. The outcomes of the current study show that further surface treatments are not necessary to achieve comparable pH stability when HA is evenly distributed throughout the entire matrix.

3.2 Characterization of the Microstructure of As-Cast Mg-1Sn-xHA Composites

In Figure 4 (A-E), we can see the as-cast microstructures of Mg-1Sn-xHA composites with various concentrations of HA. When the HA concentration increases, the grain morphology and reinforcement distribution change dramatically.

The dendritic characteristics and somewhat coarse, non-uniform grains of the base alloy are apparent in Figure 4A. (Mg-1Sn). Grain structures are bigger because there are fewer nucleation sites in the absence of reinforcement. (Mg-1Sn-3HA) in Figure 4B. A considerable amount of grain refining is achieved with the addition of 3 wt% HA. A more homogeneous microstructure is promoted by HA particles, which function as heterogeneous nucleation sites. Figure 4C (Mg-1Sn-6HA) as the nucleation density rises, a more detailed structure becomes visible, and subsequent phases are seen to be evenly dispersed. In contrast to reduced HA concentration, microstructure becomes more homogenous. (Mg-1Sn-9HA) is Figure D. With tiny equiaxed grains and negligible agglomeration, this composition displays the most polished and evenly dispersed microstructure. Grain boundary density and integrity of structure are both improved by the homogenous dispersion of HA particles. See Figure 4E for the Mg-1Sn-12HA. Particles clump together and agglomerate with increasing HA concentrations. Corrosion resistance might be negatively impacted as a result of localized homogeneity and the creation of micro-galvanic regions.

Fig 4. Characterization of the optical microstructures of Mg-1Sn-xHA composites: (A) Mg-1Sn (B) Mg-1Sn-3HA (C) Mg-1Sn-6HA (D) Mg-1Sn-9HA (E) Mg-1Sn-12HA.

3.2.1. SEM Analysis of Corroded Surfaces

SEM micrographs [Figure. 5a–e] exhibit significant changes in corrosion morphology. The Mg–1Sn alloy exhibits significant deep pitting, the formation of porous substances due to corrosion, and significant surface degradation, indicating uncontrolled dissolution. This morphology is consistent with previously described degradation characteristics of Mg–Sn alloys in PBS.

At 3 wt.% HA, shallow pits and slightly adhered corrosion debris are noted, suggesting a state of partial protection. Increasing HA to 6 wt.% leads to the formation of a denser corrosion layer characterized by a reduction in pit density. The Mg–1Sn–9HA alloy exhibits most significantly lightweight and constant corrosion substance layer, featuring cauliflower-like Ca–P-rich deposits with minimal cracking observed.

The morphology suggests that a barrier has formed and the interfacial stability has been improved. The current stir-cast 9 wt.% HA composite uses a simpler and more scalable manufacturing technique than squeeze cast or ultrasonic-assisted Mg–Sn–HA composites, yet it retains comparable surface integrity.

Partial corrosion surface decomposition and scattered cracking are seen in Mg-1Sn-12HA in contrast. One anticipating consequence of particle clustering is the formation of microstructural discontinuities, which may then be used as specific locations to start corrosion. It is clear from this finding that boosting HA content is not the only important goal improving the reinforcement is also essential.

3.3 Cytocompatibility and Cell–Material Interaction

3.3.1. Quantitative Cell Viability

The cell viability investigations [Figure 6], the Mg–1Sn alloy exhibits an approximate 74% viability, which imply moderate cytotoxic effects associated with rapid ion release and also alkalization. Significant improvements are observed as the HA content rises to 9 wt.%.

The Mg–1Sn–9HA system exhibits the most significant viability more than 95%, eclipsing a number of previously reported Mg–Sn–HA systems that were studied under identical processing conditions. The incorporation of HA has been demonstrated to improve cytocompatibility in previous investigations yet the majority of these studies have concentrated on the evaluation of single reinforcement levels. A strong correlation between the quantitative corrosion behaviour and cytocompatibility trends, along with reinforcement fraction, is established in this investigation.

Fig 5. SEM images of Mg-1Sn alloy and Mg-1Sn-xHA materials (x = 3, 6, 9, and 12 wt.%) after being immersed in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) at 37°C with scale bar representing 100 μm. (a) Mg-1Sn Alloy (b) Mg-1Sn-3HA (c) Mg-1Sn-6HA (d) Mg-1Sn-9HA (e) Mg-1Sn-12HA.

Fig 6. The cell viability of MG-63 cells cultured in the control, Mg-1Sn alloy, and Mg-1Sn-xHA composite extracts solution for 24 hours.

Viability demonstrates a modest decline to approximately 90% at 12 wt.% HA, while remaining within acceptable biomedical constraints. Degrade behaviour and biological reaction are significantly correlated, as evidenced by the observed reduction and a minor increase in surface heterogeneity and corrosion rate.

3.3.2. Optical Morphology of MG-63 Cells

Optical microscopy images [Figure 7a–f] are verified in these observations. The Mg–1Sn alloy demonstrates decreased cell spreading and an irregular morphology. HA-reinforced composites exhibit enhanced adhesion and an elongated morphology. The Mg–1Sn–9HA variant reveals dense, uniformly distributed cells characterized by prominent filopodia.

This morphology suggests beneficial surface chemistry and regulated ionic release. Improvements in cell spreading have also been observed in HA-coated Mg systems and Zn–Mg–HA hybrids. However, the current study attains these results through bulk composite development instead of modifications to the coating.

3.4 Unique Contributions and Advancement Over Existing Studies

In comparison to previous studies: Mg–Sn–HA composites produced through squeeze casting exhibited better corrosion resistance; however, there was an absence of systematic optimization of the reinforcement⁽²⁰⁾. Surface-engineered magnesium systems showed enhanced cytocompatibility; however, they recommended supplementary coating techniques⁽¹⁵⁾,⁽¹⁹⁾. Hybrid Zn–Mg–HA systems demonstrate enhanced strength and bioactivity; however, they incorporate alternative alloy chemistries that exhibit unique degradation mechanisms⁽²²⁾.

This study provides a distinctive contribution by:

1. Systematic optimization of HA content (3–12 wt.%) within the Mg–1Sn matrix.
2. Establishing a statistical correlation among mass loss, corrosion rate, pH evolution, SEM morphology, and MG-63 viability.
3. Identifying that 9 wt.% HA offers the most favourable balance among corrosion resistance and biocompatibility.
4. Validation of stir casting as a scalable fabrication method for biodegradable Mg–Sn–HA composites in industrial applications.

Fig 7. Optical images of MG-63 cells taken after 24 hours of growth in the extraction medium of several composites: (a) control, (b) Mg-1Sn alloy, (c) Mg-1Sn-3HA, (d) Mg-1Sn-6HA, (e) Mg-1Sn-9HA, and (f) Mg-1Sn-12HA.

3.5 Implications for Biodegradable Orthopaedic Implants

Controlled degradation and desirable cytocompatibility are essential in temporary load-bearing implants. Rapid degradation of materials compromises mechanical integrity, while excessive stability limits the process of bone regeneration. The Mg-1Sn-9HA composite demonstrates an optimal stable state between corrosion resistance and biological compatibility.

In this study, we found that combining Sn with HA improved corrosion resistance along with cytocompatibility in a novel manner. Incorporating HA improves bioactivity and it helps cell growth, while the Mg₂Sn phases help lower corrosion rates. By striking the optimal point between biological response and corrosion resistance, the Mg-1Sn-9HA composite exceeds all other compositions that were considered. This is because the HA particles are evenly distributed throughout the matrix, there is minimal agglomeration, and the interfacial bonding is quite good. Corrosion behavior may be negatively affected by micro-galvanic effects and minor agglomeration at higher HA contents 12 wt%. The research findings show that the Mg-1Sn-9HA composite is more effective than the traditional Mg-HA and Mg-Sn systems, which suggests that it might be a great biodegradable material for orthopaedics.

4 Conclusion

This study investigated their impact of 3–12 wt.% hydroxyapatite (HA) on the cytocompatibility and corrosion of stir-cast Mg-1Sn-xHA biodegradable composites. Research indicates HA reinforcement is essential for the biological response and degradation management in physiological contexts. Fast corrosion, pH raise and 74% cell survival were observed in the Mg-1Sn alloy. HA stabilized pH improved MG-63 cell survival and reduced mass loss is determined by Ca-P-rich surface layers.

Mg-1Sn-9HA showed best performance with a low corrosion rate, surface damage, alkalization, and cell viability at 95%. The biological impact was marginally reduced as a result of particle aggregation and corrosion caused by HA levels exceeding 12 wt%. Results indicate that deterioration and cytocompatibility are balanced by reinforcement optimization, rather than maximal addition.

The primary contribution is the identification of 9 wt.% HA reinforcement thresholds and a direct correlation between cellular response, corrosion behaviour, and composition through scalable stir-casting. In contrast to numerous studies that employ sophisticated production methods or coatings, the method for modifying degradable Mg-based implants is also efficient and industrially feasible.

The combination of Sn and HA demonstrates an approach for altering material characteristics to satisfy clinical needs through their synergistic impact. Additionally, the enhanced cytocompatibility and corrosion resistance of the fabricated composite show significant uses in orthopedics. The results of this study pave the way for more in vivo investigations and clinical translation, which in turn improves next-generation biodegradable implant materials.

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About authors: SG is a Registered Research Scholar under Annamalai University and also serves as an Assistant Professor in Sri Sai Ram Engineering College; SR serves as Professor in Annamalai University; AG serves as Associate Professor in Sri Sai Ram Engineering College; VA serves as Assistant Professor in S. S. Polytechnic College.

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